

DECORATION OF CARBON NANOTUBES WITH COPPER PARTICLES BY METAL DISPLACEMENT REACTION

G.S. Cho^{1*}, H. Jang¹, J.K. Lim¹, K.H. Choe¹, H.G. Jeong¹

¹ Eco Materials and Processing R&D Group, Korea Institute of Industrial Technology, Incheon, South Korea

* Corresponding author(gscho@kitech.re.kr)

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1 Introduction

Carbon nanotubes(CNTs) are attractive materials for several promising applications in electronic devices, thermal conductors and light-weight high strength metal matrix composites. In recent years, many efforts have led to development of various methods to obtain CNT-metal composites with excellent physical and mechanical properties[1]. The interest in CNTs as super reinforcements for aluminum(Al) has been growing and studies are largely focused on investigating their contribution to the enhancement of the mechanical performance of the metal matrix composites. In the manufacture of CNT-reinforced Al matrix composites, powder mixing and sintering processes have been widely selected and studied[2]. But the powder metallurgy needs much more processing steps and higher cost than ingot metallurgy. While in the melt and ingot route, CNTs should be modified to overcome some features like as density difference and wettability between CNTs and metal matrix. For the purpose of reducing these problems, CNTs are decorated with metal particles by physical and chemical methods[3]. In the previous report[4], CVD-grown CNTs were well deposited with nickel(Ni) nanoparticles by electroless plating method. But, the Ni element has not usually included within the standard chemical compositions of Al casting and wrought alloys. Other metal element coating on CNTs is needed to prepare CNT-reinforcement feedstock before the CNTs are mixed into Al melt.

In this study, CNTs are decorated with copper(Cu) particles with micron or submicron size to decrease the floatation of CNTs and improve the wettability between CNTs and Al melt by reducing metal salts. Generally, Cu particle deposition was performed by wet chemistry methods such as electroless plating and salt decomposition, but those techniques had many processing steps to obtain Cu-coated CNTs

composite material. So, the present paper describes a simple method to coat the CNTs using a cementation technique borrowed from extractive metallurgy[5]. In the cementation process, Cu is displaced from the copper salt by a metallic zinc(Zn) through chemical reduction. After the reaction, Cu particles are precipitated onto the CNTs by metal displacement reaction. The Cu deposited CNTs were characterized in respect of size, morphology and distributions of CNTs and Cu particles with field emission scanning electron microscopy(FESEM).

2 Experimental Procedures

CNTs used were multi-wall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) with average diameter of 10~20nm and length of 10~50 μ m(Iljin Co. Ltd., purity 99.5%) grown by CVD-catalytic process. As-prepared CNTs products were purified by refluxing in 40% nitric acid content solution for 10hr at 393K, and then the CNTs were washed several times with distilled water, and dried in vacuum. The as-received and acidified MWCNTs were shown in Fig.1. Entangled CNTs agglomerates were disintegrated by dissolving the catalytic metals. Cu particle deposition onto the CNTs was performed as follows. The pre-treated 0.1g CNTs were suspended in ethanol. Then, the copper chlorides(CuCl₂) was dissolved in the suspension containing the CNTs. The anhydrous brown CuCl₂ was used in this experiment. This suspension was ultrasonically stirred to achieve a good dispersion of CNTs. The ultrasonication was performed with applied power of 0.7kw and time of 10minutes. Then a zinc metallic powder was added to the CNTs suspension solution, while a constant temperature of 0°C is maintained. The commercial Zn flake type powder(Alfa Aesar, 99.9%)with size under 45 μ m was used. Also, Cu-CNTs composite powders obtained from evaporation of the copper

salt solution were investigated for comparison with the above displacement reaction products. Thereafter, those Cu-CNT composites were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum at 150°C for 12hrs.

Fig.1. FESEM images of (a) as-received MWCNTs and (b) as-purified MWCNTs.

The chemical compositions and appearance of the precipitated Cu particles with CNTs were identified by energy dispersive spectroscopy(EDS) and field-emission SEM analysis. Fig.2 shows the experimental flow and appearances of metal displacement reactions in this study. After Cu particles were fully displaced and precipitated, suspension turned red-brown.

Fig.2. Experimental flow and appearances of metal displacement reactions.

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Cu-CNTs composite powders after cementation process

Copper cementation is used for removing Cu^{2+} ion from electrowinning and electroplating solutions and to recover from leach solutions. Cementation is a heterogeneous electrochemical process by which Cu^{2+} is precipitated from solution on the surface of a cementation agent(e.g. iron, zinc and aluminum). Many investigators reported that cementation of copper by zinc is more effective than cementation with iron and aluminum[6]. In this study, the cementation process was used for decoration of CNTs with copper particles. The flake-type zinc powders used as displacement agent were shown in Fig.3(a) and the micrograph of Cu particles precipitated by the reaction without CNTs was shown in Fig.3(b). The all copper particles were less than 0.5 μm size. The displacement reaction occurred on the surface of Zn powders by dissolving Zn into the copper chloride solution.

Fig.3. FESEM images of (a) Zn powders used as displacement agent and (b) Cu particles displaced by cementation reaction.

The resulting FESEM morphology of Cu and CNTs composite powders after zinc displacement reaction without and with ultrasonic stirring was shown in Fig.4. The precipitated Cu particles were in the range of 100~300nm in size. CNTs were mixed with precipitated Cu nanoparticles and others were entrapped between the Cu particles or agglomerates. Some nano-sized copper particles were deposited onto the CNTs surface, but others were grown into the large Cu agglomerates by themselves without any attraction with CNTs. Also, the coverage density of CNTs surface with Cu particles was very low because the reaction occurred at the surface of Zn flake powder. By applying the ultrasonic vibration energy to the CNTs before the cementation, the coverage of CNTs surface was increased. It was attributed to an increase of active sites of broken bond on CNTs surface for the nucleation of Cu crystal.

Fig.4. FESEM images of Cu-CNTs composite powders (a) without ultrasonic stirring and (b) with ultrasonic stirring.

3.2 Cu-CNTs composite powders after evaporation process

The Cu-CNTs composite powders obtained from the evaporation of copper chloride-CNTs suspension solution was shown in Fig.5. The Cu particles were more uniformly decorated onto the CNTs surfaces than those obtained from the cementation process. It could be explained that the evaporation of solvent decrease the physical distance between copper chloride and CNTs. So, the Cu ions were precipitated on the surface of CNTs. The addition of surfactant into the suspension before the reaction would be helpful to attract the Cu ions to the CNTs surface by the arrangement of surfactant in the solution. This may be also shortened the physical distance between Cu nuclei and CNTs.

Fig.5. FESEM images of Cu-CNTs composite powders (a) without surfactant and (b) with surfactant after hydrogen evaporation of the copper chloride solution.

To increase coverage density or full crystallization on the CNTs surface will be achieved by attracting the Cu^{2+} ions to the CNTs surface. Fig.6 shows the TEM images of Cu nanoparticles and CNTs obtained from the evaporation of chloride solution. The copper particle was attached to the CNTs surface very closely. The interaction sites would be the CNTs surface defect sites, which were formed via the application of ultrasonic vibration energy on the CNTs. The copper ion will be attracted to the broken bond and crystallized at the active site.

Fig.6. TEM images of Cu-CNTs composite powders obtained from the evaporation process.

Summary

The CVD-grown multi-wall CNTs were decorated with Cu particles by metal displacement wet chemical reaction to decrease the floatation of CNTs by the density difference and increase the wettability between CNTs and Al metal melt. The ultrasonic pretreatment was performed to disperse the CNTs homogenously in the CuCl_2 solution before Zn addition. The Cu particles were displaced from the solution and deposited onto the CNTs surface. Some CNTs were remained between precipitated Cu particles, and other CNTs were entrapped within the Cu particle agglomerates. For the better deposition of Cu particles onto CNTs surface, ultrasonic vibration should be applied to the CNT suspended solution to increase the interaction sites. To increase coverage density or full crystallization on the CNTs surface will be achieved by attracting the Cu^{2+} ions to the CNTs surface. The interaction sites would be the CNTs surface defect sites, which were formed via the

application of ultrasonic vibration energy on the CNTs. The copper ion will be attracted to the broken bond and crystallized at the active site. From this study, the multi-wall CNTs have been deposited and embedded with Cu particles by chemical displacement reaction.

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